

**Vol. III
Number-1**

**ISSN No. 2319-8265
Jan. -Dec.2014**

EDUCATION TIMES

**A Peer Reviewed Journal of
Education & Humanities**

APH PUBLISHING CORPORATION

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AN OVERVIEW OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF RELATIONSHIPS

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ABSTRACT

Academic achievement in the context of relationships is a thematic paper in which the relevance of family relations, peer relations and student teacher relations in enhancing academic achievement of adolescent child is derived. Many studies have supported the claim of positive correlation between the variables which has been reflected in this paper too. The paper is designed based on three sub-titles - The concept (Family relations, Peer relations, and Student Teacher relations), Does relationship help in enhancing achievement, and Suggest some measures as to enhance develop positive relationship. The author concludes that lot needs to be done in improving family relations, peer relations and student teacher relations so as to enhance academic achievement of adolescent child.

Introduction

Achievement is not a new term in the society, and man since inception to this world is constantly trying to achieve one thing or the other. From childhood days to adulthood, academic achievement has been an important factor in students' life. So what is academic achievement all about? Academic achievement is the level of the child's performance in his academics. Performance means how well a child is able to achieve in a given time frame and academics talks about school subjects to a greater extent. Therefore performance in academics means familiarity in his school subjects. Academic achievement has obtained a state where no one can say no to it in our society. It has been deeply rooted into the psyche of every child and their parents. This has made this subject an evergreen subject for research and topic of constant scrutiny among educationist. Educationist and teachers are constantly working on strategies to improve and also to identify factors which will enhance or act as impediments to academic achievement. Many factors has been identified over the years which has some influence on academic achievement but in this article let me stick with one dimension i.e. relationships influence on academic achievement. For an adolescent child to grow in a better environment three relationships have to be in proper state. One being the member in the family his relationships between parents

and siblings has to be of good shape. Adolescents love the company of peers as it is where they enjoy sharing their energy and time the most and so peer relationship is an important factor. Further adolescent child spends most of their time in school under the watchful eyes of teacher and therefore student teacher relationship gains prominence. Hence, this article has been structured on the concept of relationships, and does it help in enhancing academic achievement and also suggest some measures to build up positive relationships. It will highlight the influence of family, peer and student teacher relationships on academic achievement of adolescents.

FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS

Humans are the most vulnerable species on the universe who needs proper care to grow from childhood to adulthood and this care is given by parents from birth and specially during adolescence and even further. Hence parents' relationship with the adolescent child is significant. Several studies have also highlighted this fact that a positive relationship between parents and children aid significantly on academic achievement. Benjamin Bloom in the Taxonomy of Educational objectives rightly puts feelings as an important factor in the development of adolescence. For all round development, and especially for academic achievement, adolescence relationship with parents is significant. Love and affection from the family will keep the adolescent child in good faith within the family.

Does family relationship help in enhancing achievement?

Studies reveal parents awareness and interest to get their wards proper education has a long lasting influence and their continuous support and encouragement and efforts to make a positive learning atmosphere for the adolescent in the family which will show better academic performance. **Chandy, Sami (1991)** in his findings state that positive family relations improve academic achievement. **Jain, Shikha (1991)** in his study on child rearing practices found parents with consistent disciplining the child was a positive factor and significantly related to academic achievement.

How to create a positive home atmosphere for a child to learn?

- Parents have to develop
- Positive relationship with children
- Create and maintain a friendly relationship with your child.
- Develop a system of open communication.
- Share responsibilities with children
- Scheduling study time, play time, and entertainment
- Constantly worked on reducing generation gap

- Maintain proper communication with school
- Listen to adolescent child's responses and feelings
- Provide diverse exposure to the adolescent child like music, dance, arts, literacy activities, philanthropy, sports and games etc.
- Judiciously take care of child's needs.
- Maintain rapport and also provide privacy as this will develop trust and train the adolescent child in becoming independent.
- Never sit with the adolescent child during learning unless it is really necessary.
- Positive encourage your child in all the aspects of life.
- The above factors will directly as well as indirectly contribute to positive home atmosphere for a child to learn.

PEER RELATIONSHIP

As the adolescent child grows into adolescence, peer groups start to influence their behavior. They start identifying with their peers and love to be in the company than their home. In this stage, the relationship finds new meaning as mutual respect, trust, independency and loyalty to their groups form shape. Their sensitivity towards every issue which matters to them will also develop during this age. Adolescence is the age of many happenings as the child forms and develops new concepts as an individual as well as a group which will virtually carry forward to the rest of their lives. Hence having comfortable peer relations will significantly contribute to positive notion about life in general.

Does peer relations influence on achievement?

Studies reveal positive peer relations influence achievement of adolescence. Peer collaboration encourages children to communicate about their strategies and solutions. It also helps them to have their own opinion and develop intrapersonal, interpersonal and social skills. When adolescents learn to communicate well with their peers their ability to manage situations which arises as they grow will also enhance. According to **Bloom (1985)**, motivation to achieve is influenced by early socialization and motivation to achieve acts as a catalyst to facilitate the transition of potentials into performance (**Gagne 1991**). Peer relations shape peer approval, self-confidence, popularity, peer acceptance, self-esteem, aggression, sacrifice, oneness, sense of pride, and loyalty etc. All of these will significantly relate to academic achievement. Peer relations can be considered as parallel relations to family relations, since it is a link between emotional dependence of adolescent child in family to the emotional independence of adolescence.

How to create positive peer relations during adolescence?

- Encourage family get-togethers.
- Motivate children in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities.
- Allow adolescent children to educational tour, and field trips organized by schools and colleges in which they study.
- Spending time with children and encourage open conversations.
- Create ample atmosphere where children work in groups. E.g. Group assignments, activity based learning, role play, simulations etc.
- Give freedom to adolescent child and also teach them to be responsible.
- Develop a culture of work while you work and play while you play.
- Motivate and support to children to harness and develop talents
- Develop trust between parents and adolescent children about peer groups.
- Develop adjustment, acceptance and accommodation values among cliques.

The above mentioned values will definitely help to have positive peer relations which in turn will influence academic achievement.

STUDENT TEACHER RELATIONSHIP

Student teacher relationship plays a vital role in the development of an individual as a whole. Many social scientists agree that the same factors which promote psychological development in home will also promote positive behavior in the classroom, which is believed to facilitate learning and achievement as school has become the second home to the adolescent child. Class teacher's enormous authority has been an outdated phenomenon. Teachers' role has changed from a task master in Gurukula system to facilitator in the classroom. A corporal punishment in school is an expired concept. Records flying and students trembling at the sight of teachers are history. Unfortunately, teacher the embodiment of truth and knowledge is also a huge question. In today's classroom, adolescent student is treated as a customer, who has to be advised, guided, counseled and treated well by giving individual attention to gain significant academic performance. He/she is open, expressive, and bold with ideas, updated with current information and tech savvy who hates authority and advice. In this changing times, student teacher relations gains significance in terms of contribution to academic achievement. The academic relation between the teacher and the student is known as teacher student relationship (**The free dictionary.com**). In modern classrooms, relationship between teacher and adolescent child involves building coalitions, among multiple contrasting groups; interact in a way that enriches each other guided by the principle of mutual trust.

Does student teacher relations influence on achievement?

When students believe that teacher is a source of knowledge and symbol of trust to look forward to, adolescent student will respect and obey the words of the teacher. A positive relationship between the two will change the teaching learning process a joyful and meaningful experience to both the teacher and student provided without compromising on the teaching learning activities. Researchers have found that teachers' attitude influence students' attitude (**Aiken, 1970**) and students' attitude have a powerful influence on their learning (**Evans, 1965**). Furthermore teacher can be a real source of inspiration if he/she is able to generate value among the students for what is taught. Moreover, when the teacher is multi-task oriented and interacts with the students without any feeling of status, power or authority, he/she will likely to have more followers among the adolescent student community. Further a teacher should act his emotions but never show real emotions to control and discipline the students and maintain a balance between discipline, sympathy and empathy. Teacher should further respect the dignity and respect of the students to gain respect and trust and should give recognition for all the good that the student has done. All these factors will contribute positively to student teacher relations. Psychologically it is a proven and accepted fact that when there is a positive relation / cause the responses will also mostly be positive. Based on the fore going, let me conclude in the lines of **Bishop and Nickson, (1983)** findings that, positive and comfortable student teacher relations significantly correlate with academic achievement of adolescent.

How to create positive student teacher relations during adolescence?

Positive relations between the student and teacher will go a long way in making classroom atmosphere healthy. Teachers' role in this aspect is higher. If a teacher can gain the trust and win the confidence of his students, students will listen and follow the instructions of the teacher. The following are some of the values a teacher should keep in mind while trying to maintain good relations with the students.

- Give freedom with responsibility so as to make them comfortable and independent. It also generates a sense of worthiness in them.
- Maintain discipline judiciously.
- Show empathy to students needs.
- After school hours interact and if possible involve students in games along with teachers.
- Maintain proper communication with students by allowing the students to express their feelings within the accepted norms and standards of the society.
- Never show partiality and always stand for the right cause as this will win trust on the teacher.
- Provide necessary guidance, support and needed information to students where ever necessary in all possible aspects.
- Being role model to the students.
- Never lose temper with the students while punishing.

- Maintain democratic style of functioning when dealing with students.
- Teach the concepts in simple and interesting way.
- Participate with students in organizing co-curricular, extra-curricular activities.

Conclusion

This term academic achievement has been for the good or bad became the crazy or most popular term in the lives of every child and their parents. Educationist, teachers, students and their parents want their child to be academically better. Research has shown that there is a positive correlation between family relations, peer relations and student teacher relations on academic achievement. Hence it is the need of the hour to focus on improving and enhancing adolescents' relationships within the family, peer groups and with their teachers all of which has its base on Taxonomy of educational objectives, so as to improve the academic achievement of adolescents in a comprehensive manner.

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Keywords: Overview, academic achievement, context, relationships.

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